

Executive summary

Objectives: Examine the role of sheep movements in the dissemination and transmission of helminths and anthelmintic resistance in UK flocks through examination of material sheep samples from livestock markets. Develop knowledge exchange strategies to disseminate the findings to relevant stakeholders through the various network available to the applicants.

Findings: This study, the largest undertaken in the UK, used parasitological techniques in conjunction with next generation sequencing in traded sheep to explore the current roundworm epidemiology and potential risk in roundworm and white drench resistance transmission associated with animal movements and/or wildlife interactions. Moderate to high strongyle prevalence were observed in all groups of sheep with an average faecal egg count (FEC) of around 220 eggs per gram (epg), moderate/high *Nematodirus* prevalence was also observed. In addition to exploring the current epidemiology, comparisons to previous studies of this type, and historical species data collected over the last century could be made. By better understanding the similarities and changes it is possible to assess the risks posed through the introduction of traded sheep on to farm and the development of informed recommendations around quarantining and treatment. The findings currently support industry recommendations to quarantine treat new and retuning stock on farm, and to check the efficacy of treatments.

Teladorsagia was the predominant genera found in sheep. This finding fits with recent epidemiological studies and again highlights the need to undertake effective quarantine treatments as they are these roundworms are the most pathogenic, cause the greatest economic losses and are the most likely to harbour resistance genes, as was highlighted by the benzimidazole resistance mutation work. Overall, high prevalence of 1-BZ resistance genes were found in the sheep roundworm species *T. circumcincta*, *T. axei*, *T. colubriformis*, and *H. contortus*. *T. circumcincta* had the highest prevalence and frequency of genes for resistance. The findings are useful in they highlight (a) times of year when species like *T. circumcincta* are important, namely late spring, where white drenches may be less useful or require monitoring to ensure that they are effective. (b) that the treatment for other roundworm species may continue to be effective. (c) the complexity of the situation facing farmers and (d) highlights the importance of forecasting tools (such as SCOPS; <https://www.scops.org.uk/forecasts/nematodirus-forecast/>) to aid treatment decisions in addition to efficacy testing.

Future research questions could focus on questions such as (a) Qualitative and/or quantitative research into farmers attitudes and behaviour to (i) better gauge the current knowledge of roundworm infections and risks posed by the movement of animals and (ii) understand farmers' reasoning for their transportation trends. (b) Use the biobank of material to investigate AR to additional anthelmintic classes as molecular markers become available and the genetic structure of resistant populations to determine likely origins and dissemination of resistance (c) Empirically assess model outputs to assess on farm outcomes of parasite movement with livestock.

Introduction

Livestock are infected with numerous gastro-intestinal roundworm species which can cause a range of clinical manifestations, from acute disease (with high levels of morbidity and/or mortality) to sub-acute disease where production losses occur. In the UK *Teladorsagia circumcincta*, *Ostertagia ostertagi* and *Nematodirus battus* are arguably the three most economically important of the 15-20 roundworm species of livestock. Although different roundworms have different epidemiology, they exist as complex, interacting communities that are traditionally treated using chemicals called anthelmintics. We currently have five main broad-spectrum classes of anthelmintic. Unfortunately resistance to these products is becoming more prevalent in all roundworms, but at different levels for each species, on each farm. Within sheep, cases of multiple resistances to many of the broad-spectrum anthelmintic classes available in the UK are commonplace whereas the first case of white drench (1-BZ) resistant *N. battus* was only reported in 2011. *Teladorsagia* and *Nematodirus* are therefore at two ends of the anthelmintic resistance spectrum in the UK with other species like *Trichostrongylus vitrinus* in the middle. As such, developing sustainable control strategies that best utilise the small number of active compounds available is essential but difficult.

Materials and methods

Gastro-intestinal nematode (GIN) faecal egg counts: Faecal egg counts (FEC), with a sensitivity of up to one egg per gram (EPG), were performed on individual samples (where applicable) using a modified salt floatation cuvette method as described by Jackson and Christie 1982. *Trichostrongyle* spp. and *Nematodirus* spp. were enumerated separately based on morphology, the presence/absence of *Moniezia* (tapeworm), *Strongyloides*, *Trichuris* (whipworm) and coccidia species were also noted in the sample.

GIN egg DNA extraction: Faecal samples which had positive strongyle counts, and from which >150 total eggs would be expected to be recovered, were subject to mass egg extraction. Eggs were extracted using differential sieving and stored at -20°C until processing for DNA extraction. DNA from roundworm eggs was extracted from ruminant samples using a proteinase K digestion. Faecal samples from culled deer were processed using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen) following manufacturers protocol. All DNA samples were purified by magnetic beads using the MagMax-96 Express (ThermoFisher, Inc.).

Deep Amplicon sequencing (DAS): Amplicons (DNA fragments produced by PCR) of the ITS-2 (for species identification) and β -tubulin isotype 1 (to assess the presence of mutations associated with BZ-resistance) genes were generated, pooled to create libraries of up to 384 populations and submitted for next generation sequencing using the Illumina MiSeq platform at Edinburgh Genomics. The sequence data was run through two pipelines that were developed by the University of Calgary and adapted for use in the Moredun Lab. The outputs allowed for the quantification of all major ruminant livestock species and also investigation of mutations in the isotype 1 β -tubulin gene associated with benzimidazole resistance.

Pipeline development: All sequence analysis pipelines for species identification and benzimidazole resistance were built and run on the Moredun Linux servers. Programs required for alignment, quality control, nematode species identification and mutation identification/grading within the β -tubulin gene were identified and installed on the in-house Linux server. A Python shell was written to enable

automated running of the pipeline; the commands directed outputs from the various different software packages into the next one and allowed for parallel running of the 384 populations at once. Two pipelines were built; one to analyse the ITS-2 data for species ID and one to assess SNPs associated with BZ-resistance (β -tubulin data). Each pipeline compares the generated sequences to databases of sequences of known species/anthelmintic susceptibility to identify the component species of the DNA pool and to pull out any mutations present. This method is capable of identifying all of the known important single nucleotide mutations associated with benzimidazole resistance in a total of 11 gastrointestinal nematode species commonly infecting ruminants (*Cooperia oncophora*, *Cooperia punctata*, *Cooperia pectinata*, *Cooperia curticei*, *Haemonchus contortus*, *Haemonchus placei*, *Teladorsagia circumcincta*, *Ostertagia ostertagi*, *Trichostrongylus axei*, *Trichostrongylus colubriformis* and *Trichostrongylus vitrinus*).

Results

Faecal samples were collected from breeding and store animals being sold through 13 different marts and included a range of breeds and ages of animals.

Faecal analysis: Pooled faecal samples from 496 sheep populations were collected from 13 marts and assessed for trichostrongyle and *Nematodirus* eggs (as well as *Trichuris*, *Monezia*, coccidian oocysts, and lungworm). Populations sampled included breeding stock and store lambs of several breeds from commercial and pedigree flocks. Strongyle eggs were highly prevalent; identified in 447 (90%) of the pens tested, this varied from 33-100% of the samples collected during each mart visit. Mean FECs were ~220 eggs per gram (range 0-11,268; Figure 2). *Nematodirus* eggs were identified in 185 (37%) of samples tested, mean of 9 eggs per gram of faeces (range 0 – 216). Samples were collected from a spread for host ages (lambs 26% of sample; 1-2 yr olds 29% and adults 45%) and enterprise type (86% commercial and 14% pedigree).

Figure 2. Violin plot of individual population trichostrongyle faecal egg counts, displayed as mart. The faecal egg count of 11,268 eggs per gram has been removed from the graph to improve graphical representation. The black and red points shows the mean and median respectively with standard error of the means.

Species profile: Individual species composition profiles were generated from 262 populations, an example cohort of individual samples are shown in Figure 3a. The composited overall results are illustrated in Figure 3b.

T. circumcincta was the most prevalent species, identified in all samples tested (n = 262) comprising 57% of the overall composition (range 1-99%). *T. vitrinus* was found in varying abundance at 18% of

the total composition (range from 0-98%). Moderate-low levels of *Chabertia ovina*, *Oesophagostomum venulosum* and *T. colubriformis* were found at 6% (0-61%), 8% (0-61%) and 5% (0-97%) respectively. Two percent of the composition was made up of *T. axei* (0-23%), the same for *Haemonchus contortus* (0-73%) and *Cooperia curticei* (0-86%). Less than one percent of the composition was made up of *Bunostomum tigenocephalum* (0-3%) and *Cooperia oncophora* (0-22%).

Figures 3 a & b. (a) Examples of individual percentage species composition profiles and (b) overall species composition profiles.

Benzimidazole resistance allele profiles: Mutations at codon positions 167, 198 and 200 were found in four of the trichostrongyle species: *T. circumcincta*, *T. axei*, *T. colubriformis* and *H. contortus*; no mutations were found in the other species. As seen in Figure 4 *T. circumcincta* had the highest SNP frequency overall, with the vast majority of worm populations carrying the genes that confer 1-BZ resistance. The specific mutations and associated amino acid changes were F167Y, E198L and F200Y (where the letters represent the amino acid changes (from and to) and the number represents the codon position e.g. Mutation F200Y, is a substitution of phenylalanine (F) with tyrosine (Y) at codon 200). Other potential mutations at position 198 (E198A, E198K, E198V) were not found in the samples.

Figure 4 shows example resistance profiles for three of the commonly associated mutations for benzimidazole resistance, namely at codons 167, 198 and 200 of the β -tubulin isotype 1 gene in *T. circumcincta*, *T. colubriformis* and *H. contortus* populations respectively.

Figure 4. Benzimidazole resistance and susceptible allele frequency profiles for *Teladorsagia circumcincta*, *Haemonchus contortus* and *Trichostrongylus colubriformis* isolated from faecal samples.

Discussion

The project provided the most comprehensive and up-to-date data on the prevalence and scale of roundworm infections in traded sheep. Moderate to high strongyle prevalence were observed in sheep with an average faecal egg count of ~220 eggs per gram (epg), moderate/high *Nematodirus* prevalence was also observed.

Different roundworm species have different natural sensitivities to the various anthelmintics, develop resistance at different rates and interact with each other within the host. As such it is important to know what roundworms are present within animals coming on to, and moving around, a farm to enable the development of a better understanding of which parts of a farm carry the greatest risk to naive stock. Additionally changing climate and management strategies have impacted on parasite epidemiology e.g. changes in spatial and temporal distribution of parasites such as *Haemonchus* and *Nematodirus* (Van Dijk et al., 2008; Bartley et al., 2021). Sustainable nematode control in livestock is heavily reliant on the use of anthelmintic treatments. A changing pattern of nematode epidemiology is making product choice decisions more difficult. The ability to identify parasite eggs at the species/genus level enables farmers/vets to make better informed treatment choices, optimise drug use. The information is invaluable in determining when and where to treat animals and with what product and thus increasing animal welfare and productivity. Quantifying the species of nematodes present in a faecal sample has for a long time been the 'holy grail' for many veterinary parasitologists, currently the work either requires the culturing of eggs to

infective larvae followed by microscopic analysis by a highly trained parasitologists or the extraction of DNA followed by molecular analysis.

Teladorsagia circumcincta was the most abundant species in sheep throughout the datasets, with lower levels of *Trichostrongylus* species, *Haemonchus contortus*, *Chabertia ovina*, *Oesophagostomum venulosum* and *Cooperia curticei*. Although low levels of *H. contortus* were seen within the dataset, the presence of *H. contortus* within the autumn and winter is consistent with recent studies. The findings are important since resistance to all classes of anthelmintics was first identified in the UK in *T. circumcincta* and *H. contortus*. Additional to that, they are also arguably the most pathogenic roundworms in the UK causing significant health and welfare concerns and economic losses if not controlled effectively.

Mutations associated with BZ resistance were found to be highly prevalent in traded sheep, particularly in *T. circumcincta*. In agreement with previous studies over the last decade, resistant mutations were identified in >70% of *T. circumcincta* populations at an average frequency of ~50%. Mutations were also identified in *T. axei*, *T. colubriformis*, and *H. contortus*, albeit at lower levels. The F200Y mutation was the most prevalent, particularly in *T. circumcincta* and *Trichostrongylus* spp., E198L was abundant in *T. circumcincta* only and F167Y was primarily found in *H. contortus*, highlighting how AR develops independently in each roundworm species. BZ-r mutations were found at a low prevalence in *T. axei* at positions 198 and 200, however where identified, the mutations were at a high frequency. These findings reconfirm the importance of effective biosecurity when introducing animals to farm. Although a moderate proportion of the species composition in traded sheep was *T. vitrinus*, no SNPs were identified in this species, highlighting that white drenches would likely be highly effective against this roundworm species. One question that is not answered with the current data is what the actual state of BZ efficacy is in UK sheep flocks, although the genetic determinants of BZ resistance are well understood, particularly around the P200 mutation, we did not undertake any efficacy testing. The presence of the other SNP variations is more complex with conflicting outcomes in different species. That said, the findings are useful in a number of ways as they highlight (a) the importance of effective quarantine treatments, and associated efficacy testing; (b) that at times of year when species like *T. circumcincta* are important, namely late spring, white drenches may be less useful or require monitoring to ensure that they are effective. Nonetheless, the advice for *Nematodirus* treatment remains the use of BZs because resistance in this parasite species is still uncommon (Melville *et al.*, 2020) (c) the treatment of other roundworm species may continue to be effective, (d) the complexity of the situation facing farmers and the need to use forecasting tools (such as SCOPS; <https://www.scops.org.uk/forecasts/nematodirus-forecast/>) to aid treatment decisions in addition to efficacy testing. Additionally, the findings provide some information on the state of BZ resistance in UK sheep roundworm populations. Albeit that the study only examined BZ resistance, due to the fact that the molecular markers for BZ exist, there is an increase in the reports of cases of multiple class resistance across the country in many different roundworm species. There is a need for further research to elucidate useful phenotypic and/or genotypic markers for other classes of anthelmintic. It is only when these markers become available that we will be able to determine how our pre-existing resistance mechanisms will impact upon the longevity of new compounds that may be brought to the market

Implication of Results

The outputs of this diverse project support the UK livestock sector by:

- Creating robust empirical evidence base of the risk posed by animal movement and providing a snapshot of the current state of BZ resistance in key roundworms of livestock